

BASIC REQUIREMENTS FOR PROCESSING AND WORKING BODIES FOR ROWS OF VINEYARDS

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Vineyard soil, which is in a state of pure fallow, must be cultivated to protect the vines from weeds. But such soil must be constantly cultivated for another reason. Rain causes compaction and washing away of most soils, and when they dry out, a crust forms on them, as a result of which ventilation of the soil is difficult and evaporation of moisture increases. If a crust forms on bare soil, 50-70% of the moisture is lost through evaporation through its surface, and only an insignificant part is consumed and evaporated by the plants. Numerous studies have established that even in well-cultivated soil, 25% of the total amount of precipitation evaporates directly from the soil and only 75% of the moisture is evaporated by the plants. If we could prevent evaporation of moisture by covering the soil, this would allow us to provide the plants in the covered areas not with 75%, but perhaps 95% of the total amount of precipitation. And in dry years, an increase in the amount of moisture by 20% gives the same increase in dry matter mass and yield.

The main task of maintaining and cultivating the soil in vineyards is to create favorable thermal, water, air, and nutrient conditions for the growth, development, and fruiting of the bushes. This is achieved by deep autumn or spring tillage, spring-summer cultivation, and periodic deep loosening (plantation renewal), the use of green manure crops, herbicides, taking into account the soil and climatic conditions of growth and cultivation methods. The soil in vineyards is usually kept in a state of black fallow. In autumn, plowing is carried out to a depth of 22-25 cm or chisel cultivation to a depth of 25-30 cm. With a row spacing of 2.5-3 m, the PRVN-2.5A or PRVM-ZA plow-loosener is used, 3.5-4 m - PRVM-4. In the zone of covering viticulture, autumn plowing is combined with covering the bushes with earth. In uncovered viticulture areas, chisel tillage is carried out in the spring to a depth of 18-22 cm with harrowing and inter-bush soil cultivation, and then during the summer the inter-rows are cultivated 3-5 times. The depth of the first cultivation is 12-14 cm, and the subsequent ones are gradually reduced to 6 cm. This prevents the formation of a compacted layer and reduces soil drying.

The rows and inter-rows are cultivated using the PRVM-ZA plough-loosener with the PRVM-11000 attachment. Instead of cultivation, good results are obtained (especially in dry conditions) by cultivating the soil with flat cutters of the KPG-2.2 type with light harrows attached to them. In the zone of covering viticulture, the first spring cultivation begins with plowing the inter-rows into a mound and plowing the covering shafts. Then the soil surface is leveled by chisel-plowing. In areas with good moisture supply (Transcarpathia) and in irrigated vineyards, the soil maintenance system includes growing green manure (winter rye or a mixture of rye with winter vetch, triticale, lupine, peas, etc.), which are a good means of replenishing organic matter, improve the physical properties of the soil and protect it from erosion. Lupine (in Transcarpathia) is sown at the end of July, and winter crops in August-September across the row spacing using a grain seeder of the SZS-2.1 type and other devices. An unseeded zone is left at a distance of 50-60 cm from the bushes. On poor soils, nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium are added between the rows at 60-90 kg/ha before sowing green manure. Winter crops are plowed in April of the following year, and spring crops are plowed in October-November of the current year to a depth of 20-23 cm and phosphorus-potassium fertilizers are added (at 90-120 kg/ha).

When applying the covering, it is necessary to avoid coating the slabs with any dark composition, such as resin and the like, otherwise they will heat up so much that they will cause burns to the trunks and hanging shoots. In my first attempts at covering the soil, I used roofing felt and made several unpleasant discoveries. The felt wears out very easily, the bunches are burned by the volatile substances released from it, and, finally, it is often blown away by the wind.

In most cases, a tall-stemmed crop allows for soil cultivation by live draft animals or machines.

With a tall-stemmed crop, I use the following soil cultivation system. In spring, the soil on large plots is loosened with a large plough to a depth of 15 cm. On small high-trunk vineyards, as well as on low trellis plantings with dense planting, the soil is ploughed in spring with a Steltz wheel plough (grape plough), harnessed by a horse or ox. In this case, the plough plows away the soil from the bushes, which was rolled up to them in the autumn. This plough can pass at a distance of 10 cm from the trunks, so that only a narrow strip of uncultivated soil remains in the row. Completely unhilling the bushes, if at all necessary, can be done during pruning. On all cohesive soils, spring ploughing of

vineyards is not necessary. Soil ploughed in the autumn freezes well in winter, it has an excellent structure, which does not need to be destroyed. In this case, even on heavy and stony clay soils, the upper layer, several centimeters thick, becomes loose and soft and acquires a lumpy structure, due to which water evaporation decreases and gas exchange increases. When the layer is turned over, this layer is destroyed and the damp and cohesive soil of the lower horizon is brought to the surface. If, in addition, the soil after plowing remains in large lumps, in windy weather it often dries out to the full depth of cultivation in just one week. Thus, part of the winter precipitation is lost. By weighing, I found that soil ploughed in the spring loses 22 liters of water per 1 cubic meter in five warm and windy days, which is 22 mm of precipitation, i.e. approximately as much as falls in one good rain.

Fig. 1. The soil processed by the planet does not have a plow furrow and is covered with a loose layer.

In the hilly mountains of Transcarpathia, to prevent water erosion, it is possible to sod (grass) the soil of vineyards in individual row spacings (in the third or fifth) by sowing cereal and legume perennial grasses (ryegrass, meadow fescue, clover, sainfoin, etc.) in spring or summer. For their better growth, mineral fertilizers are applied before cultivation or disking at the rate of 60-90 kg/ha of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium. The best results are achieved by sodding with a mixture of ryegrass and clover in every 3-5th row spacing for 2-3 years. During the summer, the grass is mown three times for mulch using specially made rotary mowers or converted tractor mowers of the KIR-1.5 type.

After 2-3 years, the grass is plowed in the fall and the next row spacings are sown. With this system of soil maintenance, its fertility increases and its structure improves due to the replenishment of organic matter due to sown grasses.

The plantation is renewed periodically once every 2-4 years through the row spacing by loosening the soil to a depth of 50-60 cm with the simultaneous application of fertilizers using PRVN-53000. With three-line loosening, its depth is up to 60 cm in the middle of the row spacing and up to 30 cm on the sides along the tracks of the caterpillars and tractor wheels. In recent years, a soil-cultivating bracket of the PRVM-15 type has been used in wide-row vineyards, which provides better quality of soil loosening. In irrigated vineyards of the steppe zone of Ukraine, cultivated on chernozem and chestnut soils, as well as on clay soils of Transcarpathia, the plantation is renewed once every two years through the row spacing in order to improve the physical properties of the soil, air exchange, moisture accumulation and protection from erosion on slopes with contour and transverse placement of rows. The effectiveness of deep loosening in vineyards increases with the combined use of mineral fertilizers. In the conditions of chernozem and dark chestnut soils of Crimea, on the recommendation of the Crimean Agricultural Institute, some farms practice annual moldboard-less two-row loosening of the soil to a depth of 55-60 cm with the arrangement of rows along the tracks of the tractor's passage in order to purposefully form a deeper root system in the active soil layer. Loosening begins in the fall after harvesting and simultaneously applying fertilizers. In irrigated areas, moisture-charging irrigation is carried out along slits and furrows. The PRVM-ZA plow-ripper with a set of various attachments is used for mechanized soil cultivation. The machine processes row spacings from 2.5 to 3 m wide. The machine frame is sliding, which allows for easy change of the implement grip during plant vegetation and when changing the row spacing. The main working bodies are universal and are used for cultivation, chisel cutting and plowing. It is aggregated with T-70S, T-54V, DT-75 and T-150 tractors. The universal working body PRVM-ZA consists of a curved stand, on the shoe of which long (paw grip 500 mm) and short (paw grip 280 mm) ploughshares are attached. For plowing, moldboards are installed on the same stand. The implement grip width is changed by turning the screw rods connected to the tractor hitch. For inter-bush cultivation of vineyards, the PRVM-ZA plough-loosener is equipped with the PRVM-11000 device. This is a hydromechanical device containing rotary flat-cutting paws for processing in rows, controlled

from the tractor hydraulic system by means of GA-34 hydraulic distributors and the DSSh-14.56.001 power hydraulic cylinder. The control signal is supplied to the distributor by a probe installed in front of the paw and interacting with the plant. The probe is made double-hinged, therefore, in addition to turning in the horizontal plane when going around the bushes, it can move in height and copy the soil surface in the row. The interaction of the probe with the control valve, hydraulic cylinder and paw is performed by a tracking system with feedback. This ensures a clear correspondence between the movements of the probe and the paw with a minimum protective zone.

For soil cultivation in wide-row vineyards with row spacing of 3.5 and 4 m, the PRVM-4 plough-loosener is recommended for production. It is based on the PYZM-ZA frame, which is supplemented with removable extensions of the longitudinal bars, two working bodies and extended screws for adjusting the grip width. PRVM-4 is equipped with working bodies and mechanisms for inter-bush soil cultivation of the PRVM-11000 type, moldboards for plowing vineyards and PRVM-53000 rippers. The PRVM-4 support wheels are installed on attached widening frames to reduce the unevenness of the working bodies. Deep loosening of the soil between the rows is performed by the PRVM-53000 device. It is a central L-shaped ripper, in which the vertical knife turns into an inclined one between the ripper stand and the chisel. Traces of caterpillar tracks and tractor wheels are loosened by two main loosening paws PRVM-ZA. The prospective system of machines will include a soil-cultivating bracket of the PRVM-15 type, which provides significantly higher volume and quality of soil loosening, instead of the flat loosener PRVM-53000 for deep loosening of vineyards

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